

Improving Surveillance in a Barangay: A Study on Assessing Needs for Designing Optimal Closed-Circuit Television Camera Placement

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This study aimed to conduct a needs assessment in order to design a CCTV camera placement plan in a barangay to enhance community safety and security. Employing a descriptive research design, the study involved 300 randomly selected respondents from a barangay in Talugtog, Nueva Ecija, Philippines. The results of the needs assessment underscored the importance of developing a CCTV camera placement plan for the barangay. The researcher proposed to develop a plan that aims to provide measures to improve safety and security within the community. Based on the needs assessment that has been conducted, several recommendations were drawn. Firstly, it was strongly advised to design a CCTV camera placement plan in the barangay. A follow-up study may be conducted focusing on this aspect. Future researchers must strategically place the CCTV in the area to optimize its full potential for securing the community. Secondly, community engagement and collaboration were highlighted as crucial factors for successful implementation, emphasizing the importance of involving community members, stakeholders, and educational institutions in the planning process. Thus, when designing a strategic CCTV placement plan, the involvement of various stakeholders is highly encouraged. Further, allocating resources for installation, maintenance, and monitoring was also proposed to ensure the sustainability and effectiveness of the surveillance system. Lastly, continuous evaluation and improvement of the CCTV camera placement plan when implemented is highly recommended, emphasizing the need for regular reviews, resident feedback, and performance monitoring to optimize the system's functionality. These recommendations provide valuable guidance for barangay officials in their pursuit of enhanced safety and security. By implementing the proposed plan that may be developed through this study and considering the input of the community, the barangay can create a safer environment and promote a sense of security among its residents.

Keywords: Closed-Circuit Television Camera, Developmental Research, Needs Assessment, Placement Plan, Surveillance.

Suggested Citation: C.N.P. Olipas, "Improving Surveillance in a Barangay: A Study on Assessing Needs for Designing Optimal Closed-Circuit Television Camera Placement," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 2(1), pp. 4-12, Jan-Feb 2024. DOI: [10.59324/ejaset.2024.2\(1\).01](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(1).01)

INTRODUCTION

As the world continuously evolves and develops new technologies for the improvement of communities and individuals from all walks of life, it is necessary to keep pace and adapt these innovations for the common good, creating a more comfortable and secure way of life. The significant contribution of the internet to improving lives has been well documented [1]. With the integration of various technologies, new innovations have become increasingly relevant in today's generation. One such innovation that has emerged prominently over the years is the use of closed-circuit television (CCTV) cameras in communities, owing to their substantial contribution to community development.

CCTV, or closed-circuit television, plays a crucial role in enhancing community safety and security [2]. By actively monitoring public spaces and sensitive areas, CCTV helps deter criminal activities, identify perpetrators, and provide crucial evidence for investigations [3]. These benefits have been

supported by a systematic review conducted in 2009, analyzing rigorous studies on the crime prevention impact of CCTV in the United States (US) and United Kingdom (UK), which found a modest reduction in various crimes, particularly theft and robberies in specific areas [4].

The use of CCTV in communities connects directly to the discussion on embracing new technologies for the common good, as it contributes to creating a safer environment for residents and visitors alike [5]. By incorporating CCTV systems, communities can tap into the power of technology to enhance safety measures and deter potential criminal activities. The active surveillance provided by CCTV cameras acts as a deterrent, making individuals aware that their actions are being recorded, which can lead to swift identification and apprehension.

Furthermore, studies conducted by Park et al. [6], Cho and Park [7], and Vilalta et al. [8] assert that CCTV systems have proven effective in preventing and reducing various types of crimes, such as theft, vandalism, and assault. These findings support the idea that the use of CCTV actively promotes a more secure and comfortable way of life for community members. Moreover, the availability of CCTV footage can assist law enforcement agencies in their investigations, enabling them to gather crucial evidence and enhance their efficiency [9]. By actively embracing the use of CCTV in communities, authorities can improve their crime-solving capabilities, ensuring justice for victims and maintaining public safety.

While there is an existing body of research on CCTV's effectiveness in enhancing surveillance and security, there is a research gap when it comes to enhancing surveillance in a barangay, specifically. The unique characteristics of barangays, such as population density, socioeconomic factors, and specific community dynamics, pose distinct challenges in terms of crime prevention and maintaining public safety. Thus, there is a need for a focused study that assesses the specific needs when designing the appropriate placement of CCTV cameras in the context of a barangay.

Conducting this study would provide valuable insights into the factors that affect the effectiveness of CCTV surveillance in a barangay. Furthermore, it would serve as a basis for barangay officials to implement the technology and reap its positive impact. Designing the appropriate placement of CCTV cameras involves considering factors such as optimal coverage of critical areas, addressing blind spots, respecting the privacy concerns of residents, and ensuring cost-effectiveness. These factors may differ significantly in a barangay compared to larger urban or commercial areas, requiring a tailored approach to the design and implementation of CCTV surveillance. Through this study, the feasibility of pursuing such a project in a specific community can be realized.

In conclusion, conducting a study focused specifically on enhancing surveillance in a barangay by assessing the needs for appropriate placement of CCTV cameras would fill the research gap and provide valuable insights into effective strategies for enhancing safety and security in this specific context. By recognizing the importance of incorporating closed-circuit television systems in communities, residents can actively enhance safety, deter criminal activities, and contribute to a more secure and comfortable way of life, ultimately serving the common good.

Statement of the Problem

In general, this study sought to conduct a needs assessment and design a plan for CCTV camera placement in a barangay to serve as a basis for implementing a surveillance and security measure within the community. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following:

1. How may the demographic profile of the respondents be described in terms of
 - a. Age; and
 - b. Sex?
2. How may the need for a well-designed CCTV camera placement plan to improve safety and security in the barangay be described in terms
 - a. Perception of Safety and Security;
 - b. Crime Incidents and Patterns; and
 - c. Coverage and Surveillance Needs?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study employed a descriptive research design. Descriptive research design often refers to the process of describing and analyzing a particular group to draw valuable insights and better understand a specific population [10].

In this study, a total of 300 respondents were involved, a number considered statistically significant in consideration of the total number of residents in the barangay, as determined by the researcher. These respondents were bona fide residents of Barangay Nangabulan, Talugtug, Nueva Ecija, Philippines. The researcher employed a random-sampling technique to reduce bias and ensure that all groups in the barangay had equal chances of being involved as respondents in this study.

The study commenced with an initial interview conducted by the researcher with concerned officials, such as the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK). The SK chairperson was interviewed, aiming for possible collaboration, as the study's results were intended to provide a basis for future SK projects in the barangay. After a series of interviews and observations in the barangay, the researcher began reviewing relevant studies and literature. Simultaneously, the researcher crafted the survey instrument. To ensure the validity and reliability of the research instrument, the researcher conducted pilot testing with 30 non-respondents over a separate period of time. The researcher also implemented several measures to assess the validity, reliability, and acceptability of the items included in the self-made instrument. The researcher performed a reliability analysis and presented the results in Table 1. The reliability analysis indicates that all three scales demonstrate satisfactory levels of internal consistency, with the Perception of Safety and Security and Crime Incidents and Patterns scales showing good reliability and the Coverage and Surveillance Needs scale demonstrating acceptable reliability. These results support the use of these scales in assessing the relevant constructs in the study.

Table 1. Reliability Analysis

Scale	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Reliability Level
Perception of Safety and Security	5	0.83	Good
Crime Incidents and Patterns	5	0.88	Good
Coverage and Surveillance Needs	5	0.77	Acceptable

From September 2022 to December 2022, the actual data gathering took place. The researcher handed out the survey questionnaires to randomly chosen respondents. The instrument consisted of two parts. The first part covered the demographic profile of the respondents, while the second part assessed the need to design a CCTV placement plan to further improve the safety and security of the residents in the barangay.

The researcher assured the respondents that no personal information would be collected and that their responses would not directly identify them. Furthermore, utmost anonymity and confidentiality were observed, and the collected data were solely used for the purpose of this study. After data collection, the researcher employed statistical treatment using Software Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23. Statistical treatments, such as percentage distribution and mean, were used to analyze the collected data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following figures and tables present the results of the study conducted. Figures 1 and 2 illustrate the distribution of responses among different sexes and age groups, providing insights into the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Tables 2, 3, and 4 present the descriptive statistics of key variables, offering a comprehensive overview of the collected data. These visual representations and numerical summaries offer valuable insights into the findings and contribute to the understanding of the research outcomes.

Demographic Profile

The study involved 300 respondents, comprising 57.33% males and 42.67% females, creating a balanced representation. This balance is essential for understanding the diverse needs and perspectives of both genders within the community.

Figure 1. Percentage Distribution of Respondents by Sex

Figure 1 illustrates insights from male and female respondents regarding CCTV camera placement. The equal gender distribution ensures fairness and inclusivity in decision-making. Recognizing gender-specific concerns, the study addresses unique perspectives in designing the CCTV camera installation plan to meet the safety needs of the entire barangay.

This approach not only fosters community engagement but also promotes a democratic process in the CCTV camera placement design. The study advocates for a gender-sensitive approach, integrating gender-specific needs into planning to enhance security measures. Policymakers can use these findings to develop targeted strategies addressing safety concerns for both males and females in the barangay. The study underscores the importance of balanced representation, gender-specific considerations, community engagement, and a gender-sensitive approach in designing CCTV camera placement for the community's overall safety.

Figure 2. Percentage Distribution of Respondents by Age

Figure 2 presents a breakdown of the respondents' age distribution in the needs assessment study on CCTV camera placement in a barangay. Among the key findings, 22.00% of respondents fell in the 18–20 age group, while the 21–23 and 24–26 age groups constituted 18.00% and 13.33%, respectively. Participants aged 27–29, 30–32, and 33–35 represented 14.00%, 17.00%, and 10.67%, respectively. Additionally, individuals above 35 accounted for 5.00% of respondents.

The data in Figure 2 suggests a predominant presence of younger individuals in the study, reflecting their active involvement and strong interest in community safety and security matters. Recognizing this trend, the study emphasizes the need to consider the unique perspectives and safety

requirements of individuals across different age brackets when devising effective CCTV camera placement plans.

To ensure a more comprehensive and representative sample, it is essential to engage age groups that may be underrepresented. This can be achieved through targeted outreach efforts, including awareness campaigns, workshops, or surveys specifically tailored to older age groups. This inclusive approach aims to capture diverse insights and experiences, contributing to a more robust community safety strategy.

Incorporating the viewpoints of older age groups is crucial, as their experiences and knowledge can significantly enhance the study's findings. Their input can identify safety concerns specific to their demographic, guiding the design of CCTV camera placement plans. By involving older community members, the study ensures a safety system that caters to the entire community.

Moreover, the age distribution has practical implications for resource allocation and implementation strategies. Understanding these demographics helps guide decisions on where to concentrate CCTV cameras, especially in areas frequented by younger individuals. Additionally, the findings can shape targeted educational programs and awareness campaigns for different age groups, optimizing the CCTV surveillance system's effectiveness in promoting community safety.

Needs Assessment for CCTV Camera Placement

Table 2 provides valuable insights into the perception of safety and security in the barangay as it relates to the needs assessment for CCTV camera placement. The high mean values across all statements indicate a strong consensus among the respondents, reflecting a positive attitude towards the potential benefits of CCTV camera systems.

Table 2. Perception Regarding Safety and Security in Barangay

Item Statements	Mean	Verbal Description
1. I believe that designing CCTV camera placement plan in our barangay would enhance safety and security.	3.68	Strongly Agree
2. The presence of CCTV cameras would make me feel safer in the barangay.	3.64	Strongly Agree
3. The installation of CCTV camera is necessary to deter criminal activities in our barangay.	3.69	Strongly Agree
4. A well-designed CCTV camera system would improve the overall perception of safety in our barangay.	3.75	Strongly Agree
5. There is a need to design CCTV camera placement plan in our barangay to address security concerns effectively.	3.76	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.70	
Verbal Description	Strongly Agree	

Table 2 displays the outcomes of the needs assessment conducted by the researcher, focusing on residents' perspectives on safety and security in the barangay and the significance of CCTV for a more secure community. Respondents rated their agreement with statements about CCTV camera placement, with mean values indicating the average level of agreement. The results showed strong consensus, with mean scores ranging from 3.64 to 3.76, all classified as "strongly agree."

The majority of respondents strongly believed that designing CCTV camera placement in the barangay would enhance safety and security, aligning with findings from Cuevas et al. [11]. The researcher emphasizes CCTV's significant role in protecting the community against crimes. Residents recognized the technology's potential contribution to overall well-being and crime prevention.

The presence of CCTV cameras made residents feel safer in the barangay, supporting findings from Wu et al.'s study [12] highlighting the psychological reassurance CCTV provides. This feeling of safety can lead to increased community engagement, improved quality of life, and enhanced trust among residents. The strong agreement regarding the necessity of CCTV camera placement to deter criminal activities emphasized the importance of preventive measures. Welsh and Farrington [13] supported this, stating that CCTV technology contributes to safety and crime reduction. The researcher notes that respondents acknowledged the role of surveillance in deterring offenders,

showing support for proactive measures against crime. The high mean score for the statement about a well-designed CCTV system improving the overall perception of safety suggested that residents value both the aesthetic and functional aspects of surveillance infrastructure. This insight is crucial for thoughtful planning and integration into the urban landscape, contributing to a positive community image. Agreement that CCTV installation is needed to address security concerns highlighted a collective awareness of safety challenges. The researcher notes that residents desire proactive measures to create a safer living environment.

These results signal strong community support for implementing CCTV systems in the barangay, informing the researcher and decision-makers about readiness and willingness to embrace surveillance technology. Recognizing the high level of agreement guides planning, resource allocation, and emphasizes the importance of community engagement for transparent communication and garnering support.

Meanwhile, the results of the needs assessment in terms of crime incidents and patterns as one of the factors for installing CCTV in the barangay are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Crime Incidents and Patterns in Barangay

Item Statements	Mean	Verbal Description
1. CCTV cameras can act as a deterrent to crime and anti-social behavior in our barangay.	3.28	Strongly Agree
2. Designing a CCTV camera placement plan is necessary to improve safety and security in our barangay.	3.41	Strongly Agree
3. The frequency of crime incidents in our barangay justifies the need for a well-designed CCTV camera placement plan.	3.41	Strongly Agree
4. CCTV cameras have the potential to deter criminal activities and reduce the occurrence of crimes in our barangay.	3.25	Agree
5. The presence of CCTV cameras in our barangay would facilitate the identification and prosecution of offenders involved in criminal incidents.	3.47	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.36	
Verbal Description	Strongly Agree	

Table 3 provides information on crime incidents and patterns in the barangay, as part of the needs assessment for CCTV camera installation. The mean values represent the average level of agreement with each statement, indicating a generally positive attitude among respondents towards the role and effectiveness of CCTV cameras in addressing crime and enhancing safety and security. The mean scores, ranging from 3.25 to 3.47, show a strong level of agreement across all statements, with an overall mean score of 3.36.

The results highlight the collective belief among respondents that CCTV cameras can act as a deterrent to crime and anti-social behavior in the barangay. This understanding suggests a willingness to embrace proactive measures for maintaining a safer environment. Additionally, there is strong agreement on the necessity of designing a CCTV camera placement plan, emphasizing the recognition of the importance of a well-thought-out and strategic approach.

Respondents also strongly agree that the frequency of crime incidents justifies the need for a well-designed CCTV camera placement plan, indicating a collective awareness of existing crime patterns. While with slightly lower agreement, respondents still express belief in the potential of CCTV cameras to deter criminal activities and reduce crime occurrence, reflecting a general understanding that surveillance systems can serve as preventive measures.

Furthermore, respondents strongly agree that the presence of CCTV cameras facilitates the identification and prosecution of offenders, recognizing surveillance footage as valuable evidence for investigations. The high overall mean score of 3.36 underscores the strong agreement among respondents, signifying a high level of support for the effectiveness of CCTV camera placement in addressing crime and improving safety and security in the barangay.

These positive perceptions and high levels of agreement provide valuable insights for decision-makers and stakeholders. The information can guide planning, resource allocation, and strategic initiatives for crime prevention and community safety. Understanding this strong agreement can also help build trust and support within the community for the successful implementation of CCTV camera

placement. The findings from Table 3 contribute to evidence-based decision-making, ensuring a safer and more secure environment for residents.

Table 4. Coverage and Surveillance in Barangay

Item Statements	Mean	Verbal Description
1. There are specific areas in the barangay that require enhanced surveillance coverage for improved safety and security.	3.25	Agree
2. CCTV cameras should be strategically placed in high-traffic areas of the barangay to deter potential criminal activities.	3.23	Agree
3. It is important to identify crime hotspots and problem areas in the barangay for targeted surveillance using CCTV cameras.	3.48	Strongly Agree
4. The installation of CCTV cameras in public spaces, such as parks and plazas, would contribute to a safer environment for residents.	3.47	Strongly Agree
5. Schools and educational institutions in the barangay would benefit from CCTV camera placement to ensure the safety of students and staff.	3.44	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.37	
Verbal Description	Strongly Agree	

Table 4 displays the data concerning coverage and surveillance needs in the barangay, a crucial aspect of the needs assessment for CCTV camera placement. The mean values represent the average agreement level with each statement, offering insight into respondents' perspectives.

The overall results indicate a positive attitude toward coverage and surveillance needs in the barangay, with mean scores ranging from 3.23 to 3.48 and an overall mean of 3.37, signifying strong agreement. This high score suggests robust support for the strategic placement of CCTV cameras to address coverage and surveillance needs.

Examining the table sheds light on respondents' perceptions regarding coverage and surveillance needs in the barangay. Notably, respondents agreed on the necessity of enhanced surveillance in specific areas for improved safety and security. This emphasizes the importance of a comprehensive approach, considering distinct characteristics and vulnerabilities in different locations.

Furthermore, respondents expressed agreement that strategically placing CCTV cameras in high-traffic areas would deter potential criminal activities, emphasizing visibility and deterrence to enhance safety. There was also strong agreement on the importance of identifying crime hotspots, supporting data-driven decision-making for targeted surveillance efforts.

Respondents strongly agreed that installing CCTV cameras in public spaces, including parks and plazas, would contribute to a safer environment, acknowledging the deterrent effect of surveillance systems. Additionally, there was a strong consensus that schools and educational institutions would benefit from CCTV camera placement, emphasizing the role of surveillance in creating a secure learning environment.

These insights hold significance for designing and implementing CCTV camera systems in the barangay. Decision-makers can utilize this information to identify priority areas, strategically place cameras, and allocate resources effectively, ultimately enhancing safety measures. The findings also underscore the importance of community engagement in the planning process, ensuring that residents, stakeholders, and educational institutions contribute their perspectives. Integrating these insights into broader safety and security strategies is crucial for comprehensive crime prevention and community well-being.

CONCLUSION

This study focused on conducting a needs assessment to inform the design of a CCTV camera placement plan aimed at improving the safety and security of residents in a barangay. Using a descriptive research design, the researcher engaged 300 randomly selected respondents from a barangay in Talugtug, Nueva Ecija, Philippines. The results emphasized the importance of tailoring a CCTV camera placement plan specifically for the barangay.

In light of the study's findings, several recommendations are proposed. Firstly, it is suggested that barangay officials use the study's results to strategically plan the placement of CCTV cameras, thereby enhancing safety and security within the community. Integrating technology in this manner can contribute significantly to the residents' well-being.

Secondly, to ensure the successful implementation and acceptance of the CCTV camera placement plan, active engagement and collaboration with community members, stakeholders, and educational institutions are deemed crucial. Their input and perspectives should be considered during the planning and implementation process, fostering a sense of ownership and cooperation that allows the community to actively contribute to safety and security initiatives.

Thirdly, allocating sufficient resources for the installation, maintenance, and monitoring of CCTV cameras is essential. This involves financial allocation for high-quality cameras, infrastructure for installation, and training for personnel responsible for maintenance and operation. Continuous monitoring and maintenance are paramount to ensuring the effectiveness and longevity of the surveillance system.

Lastly, the study recommends continuous evaluation and improvement of the CCTV camera placement plan. Regular reviews of crime patterns, gathering feedback from residents, and monitoring camera performance are suggested to identify areas for improvement and optimize the functionality of the surveillance system over time.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The researcher sincerely thanks the participants for actively taking part in this study. Their time and contributions were vital in collecting the needed data and insights. Special thanks also go to Mr. John Michael P. Olipas, the SK chairperson of Barangay Nangabulan, for collaborating and sharing important information. His support greatly contributed to the success of this study.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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